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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19814385>**ANNOTATION**

Drug-induced liver injury (DILI) accounts for approximately 10% of all adverse reactions associated with pharmacological therapy. According to data from the World Health Organization, medications are responsible for 10–15% of cases of acute liver failure. The aim of this study was to compare the occurrence and features of DILI in patients with chronic viral hepatitis at fibrotic stages with those at non-fibrotic stages.

It has been well established that in chronic viral hepatitis, both direct and indirect viral effects contribute to endogenous intoxication and promote the development of liver fibrosis, thereby increasing hepatic vulnerability to drug-related injury. In this context, pharmacological agents represent an additional metabolic burden on the liver. The present study evaluated and compared cases of drug-induced liver injury in patients with advanced fibrotic stages of chronic viral hepatitis B and in patients without fibrosis.

Keywords: Chronic viral hepatitis B, non-fibrous and fibrous stages of the liver, drug-induced liver damage.

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СЛУЧАИ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННО-ИНДУЦИРОВАННОГО ПОРАЖЕНИЯ ПЕЧЕНИ НА ФИБРОЗНОЙ СТАДИИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ВИРУСНОГО ГЕПАТИТА “В”

АННОТАЦИЯ

Лекарственное поражение печени (ЛПП) составляет около 10% всех побочных эффектов, связанных с применением фармакологических препаратов. По официальным данным ВОЗ, лекарственные препараты вызывают развитие острой печеночной недостаточности в 10-15% случаев. Целью данной статьи является сравнительное изучение лекарственно-индуцированного повреждения печени (DILI-Drug-Induced Liver Injury) в фиброзных стадиях хронических вирусных гепатитов и в стадиях без фиброза. В настоящее время научно доказано, что прямое и косвенное воздействие вирусов при хронических вирусных гепатитах приводит к эндогенной интоксикации и развитию фиброза. В таких случаях лекарственные препараты, естественно, оказывают чрезмерную нагрузку на печень. Авторы изучали случаи лекарственного поражения печени (ЛПП) у пациентов с фиброзными стадиями хронического вирусного гепатита В в сравнении с без фиброзными стадиями.

Ключевые слова: Хронический вирусный гепатит В, без фиброза и фиброзная стадии печени, лекарственное поражение печени.

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**SURUNKALI VIRUSLI GEPATIT "B" NING FIBROZ BOSQICHLARIDA JIGARNI
DORI VOSITALARDAN ZARARLANISH (DILI) HOLATLARI**

ANNOTATSIYA

Jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishi (DILI) farmakologik preparatlarni qo'llash bilan bog'liq barcha nojo'ya ta'sirlarining taxminan 10% ni tashkil qiladi. JSST ning rasmiy ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, o'tkir jigar yetishmovchiligi rivojlanishiga 10-15 % holatlarda dori vositalar sabab bo'ladi. Mazkur maqolani maqsadi surunkali virusli gepatitlarning fibroz bosqichlarida jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanish (DILI- Drug-Induced Liver Injury) holatlarini fibrozsiz bosqichlari bilan qiyoslab urganishdan iborat. Hozirgi kunda surunkali virusli gepatitlarda viruslarni bevosita va bilvosita ta'siri, endogen intoksikatsiyaga va fibroz rivojlanishiga olib kelishi ilmiy jihatdan isbotlangan. Bunday holatlarda dori vositalari, jigarga ortiqcha yuk bo'lishi tabiiydir. Mualliflar surunkali virusli gepatit V ning fibroz bosqichlari rivojlangan bemorlarda, jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanish (DILI) holatlarini fibrozsiz bosqichlari bilan qiyoslab urganishgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Surunkali virusli gepatit V, jigarning fibrozsiz va fibroz bosqichlari, jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishi.

Kirish. Surunkali virusli gepatitlarda virus yuklamasini o'zi organizmning endogen intoksikatsiyasiga va fibroz rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Gepatit viruslari bevosita yoki immun vositachiligida bilvosita gepatotsitlarga zararlovchi ta'sir ko'rsatadi va endogen intoksikatsiya sindromini keltirib chiqaradi. Surunkali virusli gepatitlardagi endogen intoksikatsiya sindromi klinik ko'rinishlarsiz namayon bo'lib, jigardagi o'zgarishlarning ko'lami va chuqurligini anglatadi. Virus yuklamasining miqdori, jigarda fibroz bosqichlari rivojlanishi bilan bevosita bog'liqdir.

Jigarning dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishi (DILI) farmakologik preparatlarni qo'llash bilan bog'liq barcha nojo'ya ta'sirlarining taxminan 10% ni tashkil qiladi. JSST ning rasmiy ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, o'tkir jigar yetishmovchiligi rivojlanishiga 10-15 % holatlarda dori vositalar sabab bo'ladi.

Butun dunyoda dorivor o'simlik preparatlarini qabul qilish va biologik faol qo'shimchalar (BFQ) qabul qilish natijasidagi jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishining usishi kuzatilmoqda. AQSh da har yili jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishi tufayli 2 mingga yaqin jigar

transplantatsiyasi amaliyoti amalga oshiriladi. Jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishi chastotasi yiliga 100000 aholiga 1-19 holatni tashkil qilsa, boshqa ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, dori vositalar qo'llanilgan barcha holatlarning 3-6% tashkil etadi. Dunyoda jigar patologiyasi bilan shifoxonaga yotqizilgan bemorlar ichida, dori vositalar ta'siri natijasida kelib chiqadigan sariqlik (xolestaz) 2-5% ni, dori vositalar ta'siri natijasida kelib chiqqan gepatit 10% ni tashkil qiladi.

Xorijiy mualliflarning (Björnsson E.S., Bergmann O.M., Björnsson H.K. et al.) ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, DILI (Drug-Induced Liver Injury) dori vositalar qabul qiluvchi 100000 bemorlarning 10-20 tasida kuzatiladi, kasalxonaga yotqizilgan bemorlarda 2-5% holatlarda sariqlik keltirib chiqaradi, o'tkir gepatitlarning barcha holatlarining taxminan 10 % ni tashkil etadi, o'tkir jigar yetishmovchiligiga 11 % holatlarda sabab bo'lib, yiliga 40 000 gacha o'lim DILI tufayli yuzaga keladi. Dori vositalari jigarning surunkali zararlanishiga va yaqqol fibroz/sirroz shakllanishiga sabab bo'lishi mumkin[24].

1968- yildan beri dori vositalarining nojo'ya ta'sirlarini qayd etuvchi JSST ma'lumotlar bazasining tahlillariga ko'ra, 1990- yillardan boshlab jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanish holatlari sezilarli darajada o'sishi kuzatilgan. Ular orasida jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishida eng ko'p o'lim holatlari, asosan parasetamol, OIV infeksiyasini davolashda qo'llaniladigan preparatlar, epilepsiyaga qarshi preparatlar (valproy kislotasi), analgetiklar, tizimli antibakterial preparatlar va o'smaga qarshi dori vositalarini qabul qilishlar tufayli kelib chiqishi ma'lum qilingan.

Ingliz tilidagi adabiyotlarda bunday kasalliklarni ifodalash uchun DILI (Drug-induced liver injury), o'zbek tilidagi adabiyotlarda esa "jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishi" degan atama qo'llaniladi.

Jigarning dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishi bu retsept bo'yicha yoki retseptsiz beriladigan barcha turdagi dorilar (jumladan, kichik kimyoviy molekulalar, biologik agentlar, fitopreparatlar, parhez qo'shimchalari va biologik faol qushimchalar) tufayli kelib chiqadigan va qabul qilish boshlanganidan o'rtacha 5 kundan 90 kungacha bo'lgan davrda rivojlanadigan jigarning zararlanishidir.

Xalqaro tibbiyot fanlari tashkilotlari kengashi CIOMS (Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences) tomonidan dori vositalariga nojo'ya reaksiyalarni tavsiflash uchun alohida atamalar qabul qilingan. Sarg'aygan bemorlar uchun R ko'rsatkichini aniqlash tavsiya etilgan. $R \text{ (nisbat)} = \frac{ALT \text{ (MYUCh karraligi)}}{IF \text{ (MYUCh karraligi)}}$. CIOMS tomonidan R ko'rsatkichi bo'yicha jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan toksik zararlanishining (DILI) quyidagi tiplarga ajratish taklif etilgan.

CIOMS bo'yicha DILI tiplari.

1- jadval

Zararlanish tipi	Faollik		R
	ALT	ISh	
Gepatotsellyulyar	>2x MYuCh	< MYuCh	≥5
Xolestatik	<MYuCh	>2x MYuCh	≤2
Aralash	>2x MYuCh	>2x MYuCh	2-5

Izoh: MYuCh- me'yorning yuqori chegarasi.

Bundan tashqari, CIOMS "jigarning o'tkir shikastlanishi" atamasini kasallik davomiyligi 3 oydan kam bo'lganda, "surunkali" atamasini esa kasallik davomiyligi 3 oydan ortiq bo'lganda qo'llashni tavsiya etgan. Bu holat jigar fibrozi DILI ning hepatotsellyulyar turi boshlanganidan 3 oy o'tgach shakllanishiga asoslangan. Maddrey W.C., Boitnott J.K. lar fikricha DILI ning xolestatik turi kasallik davomiyligi 6 oy va undan ortiq bo'lganda "surunkali" atamasi qo'llaniladi. Surunkali DILI diagnozi jigarning progressiv shikastlanishini anglatmaydi[28].

DILI bo'yicha xalqaro ekspertlar ishchi guruhi tavsiyasiga ko'ra, agar dori vositasi (biologik faol qushimchalar va boshqalar) qabul qilish fonida quyida ko'rsatilgan o'zgarishlar kuzatilsa, bemorda DILI mavjud bo'lishi mumkin (tavsiyaning ishonchlilik darajasi V (dalillarning ishonchlilik darajasi 3) degan fikr yuritiladi:

- a) ALT faolligining oshishi $>2\text{MYuCh}$;
- b) yoki bog'langan bilirubin darajasining oshishi $>2\text{MYuCh}$;
- c) yoki AST, IF faolligi va umumiy bilirubin darajasi oshishining kombinatsiyasi ($\geq 2\text{MYuCh}$

ko'rsatkichlaridan biri).

Bunda jigar kasalliklarining mavjudligini hisobga olish zarur.

Agar qo'llanilayotgan dori vositasi bemor uchun hayotiy zarurat bo'lsa, u quyidagi laborator va klinik belgilar kuzatilgan holatlarda bekor qilinishi kerak bo'ladi:

- a) qon zardobida ALT yoki AST $> 8 \text{ MYuCh}$;
- b) 2 hafta va undan ortiq davrda qon zardobida ALT yoki AST $> 5 \text{ MYuCh}$;
- v) qon zardobida ALT yoki AST $> 3 \text{ MYuCh}$, bilirubin $> 2\text{MYuCh}$ yoki MNO $> 1,5$;
- g) qon zardobida ALT yoki AST $> 3 \text{ MYuCh}$, sitoliz, asta-sekin kuchayib boruvchi holsizlik, charchoq, dispepsiya simptomlari va / yoki eozinofiliya ($> 5\%$) bilan birga kelsa.

BFQ ning gepatotoksikligi odatda bemorlar va shifokorlar tomonidan yetarlicha baholanmaydi. Shu bilan birga, aholining ushbu vositalardan foydalanish chastotasi ancha yuqori. Faqat AQShda mamlakat aholisining 50-70% sog'liqni saqlash, qomat yoki turli kasalliklarni davolash uchun qo'shimcha sifatida qabul qilinishi ma'lum qilingan.

DILI ning haqiqiy tarqalganligi noma'lumligicha qolmoqda, ammo shuni ta'kidlash mumkin, klinik amaliyotda bunday diagnoz kamdan-kam hollarda asossiz ravishda qo'yiladi. Bu shartli bir nechta omillar bilan bog'liq bo'lib, ular orasida eng muhimi quyidagilardir:

- bemorlarning ba'zi dorilarni (antidepressantlar, neyroleptiklar, potensiyani oshirish uchun vositalar va boshqalar) qabul qilayotganligi to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarni istamasliklari;
- shifokorlarning yatrogen kasalliklarni hujjatlashtirishni istamasligi; - xilma-xil simptomlarni noto'g'ri talqin qilinishi.

Surunkali virusli hepatitlarda DILI sabablariga gepatotoksik preparatlar istemol qilish, turli dori vositalarni birgalikda qabul qilishlar (bir vaqtning o'zida 2-3 xil dori vositalarni qabul qilish jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanish xavfini oshirsa, 6 va undan ortiq turdagi dori vositalarni qabul qilish, jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanish xavfini 80% gacha oshiradi) kiradi. Dori dozasi va istemol qilish tartibini buzish, jigar kasalliklarini (surunkali virusli hepatitlarda dori vositalarni doimiy ravishda qabul qilishni o'zi, jigarga ortiqcha yuk bo'lishi) mavjud bo'lishi, DILI xavfini yanada oshiradi.

Hozirgi vaqtda DILI da klinik diagnoz, jigar shikastlanishining klinik belgilari, bioximik tahlillardagi dinamik o'zgarishlar, dori vositalarini haqiqiy yoki idiosinkraziyali (organizmning ba'zi dorilar ta'sirini ko'tara olmasligi yoki yoqtirmasligi) gepatotoksikligini baholash (agar buni qilish imkoniyati bo'lsa), shuningdek jigar zararlanishining boshqa sabablari inkor etilgandan keyin, bemorning "dori" anamnezi har tomonlama tahlil qilingandan so'ng, istisno tariqasida quyiladi.

Jigarda fibroz va sirroz bosqichlari mavjud bo'lgan bemorlarda DILI, jigardagi fibroz va sirroz jarayonlari o'tkir yallig'lanishigaga olib kelishi ma'lum qilingan.

DILI AQSh va Yevropada o'tkir jigar yetishmovchiligining eng keng tarqalgan sabablaridan biri hisoblanadi. Fransiya va Islandiyada o'tkazilgan so'rovlarga ko'ra, DILI har 100000 aholiga taxminan 14-19 ta holatlarda uchraydi.

G. Ostapowicz va hammualliflarning tadqiqotlariga ko'ra, DILI holatlari ayollarda erkaklarga nisbatan ko'p uchrashi, parasetamol keltirib chiqaradigan reaksiyalarning 79% va dori vositalarga idiosinkraziv reaksiyalarning 73% ayollarga to'g'ri kelganligini ma'lum qilishgan[14].

Jigarni surunkali virusli kasalliklarini davolash bo'yicha keng ko'lamda ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilishi va sezilarli darajada samara berayotganligiga qaramasdan, surunkali virusli hepatitlarni kechishiga ta'sir qiluvchi boshqa turli omillarni, masalan, jigarda fibroz bosqichlari rivojlangan holatlarda DILI masalasi bo'yicha ilmiy izlanishlar to'liq olib borilgan deb bo'lmaydi. DILI bo'yicha mavjud ilmiy maqolalar, klinik tavsiyalarni tahlil qilib chiqqanimizda ushbu masala bo'yicha biror-bir tadqiqotlar olib borilganligi to'g'risida ilmiy ma'lumotlarni topa olmadik.

Masalan, Yeremina Ye.Yu "DILI" nomli maqolasida ushbu muammo bo'yicha zamonaviy ma'lumotlar va bir qator klinik kuzatuvlar, jumladan DILI diagnostikasi va davolash masalasi, DILI ning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, uning homiladorlarda, homiladorlik muddatining uzayishi bilan

rivojlanishi, bioximik ko'rsatkichlaridagi o'zgarishlarning og'irligi bilan klinik belgilar o'rtasida qat'iy bog'liqlikning (корреляция) йўқлиги, коагулопатия хавфининг юқори бўлиши ҳақида тадқиқотлар олиб борилган [11].

Onuchina Ye.V, Rojanskiy A.A, Kazakova R.V., Poshkayte N.A. lar o'z maqolalarida DILI muammolari bo'yicha adabiyotlardagi ma'lumotlar va surunkali dori gepatiti holati uchraganligi to'g'risida ilmiy ma'lumotlar berishgan[12].

J. G. Stine va N. Chalasani ni o'zlarining tizimli sharhlarida DILI ilgari taxmin qilinganga nisbatan ko'proq uchrashi va yirik milliy reestrlari ma'lumotlariga asosan 18% gacha tarqalganligi, jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan xolestatik zararlanishi xavfi ≤ 65 yoshlilarda yuqori bo'lishi va uzoq yashirin davri (> 365 kun) davom etishi haqida ma'lum qilishgan[13].

Avdeeva M.G., Kulbujeva M.I., Kolodko Ye.I., Chernikova N.V., Zapashnyaya O.V. o'z maqolalarida DILIni klinik ko'rinishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari orasida kasallikning boshlanishi, o'rtacha xolestaz va ALT me'yordan 22 baravargacha, AST esa 9 baravargacha oshishi va GGTP ning oshishi xarakterlidir deb taqidlashgan[16].

Lazebnik L. B., Golovanova Ye. V., Хлынова O. V., Alekseenko S. A., Aryamkina O. L., Bakulin I. G., Bakulina N. V., Baranovskiy A. Yu., Bondarenko O. A., Varganova A. N., Volkova T. V., Vologjanina L. G., Volchegorskiy I. A., Demicheva T. P., Dolgushina A. I., Maev I. V., Minushkin O. N., Rayxelson K. L., Smirnova Ye. N., Tarasova L. V., syganova Yu. V. lar o'z maqolalarida DILI bo'yicha atamalar va tushunchalarga aniqliklar kiritishgan bo'lib, DILI etiopatogenezi, epidemiologiyasi, klassifikatsiyasi, klinik kurinishi, diagnostikasi, davolash hamda homilador ayollarda DILI kechishi, profilaktikasi masalalarini atroflicha bayon etishgan[3].

V.M. Chernova jigarni toksik zaharlanishi nomli o'z maqolasida yiliga dunyo bo'yicha 1 mln kishi dori vositalarni nojuya ta'siridan jabrlanishi, 180000 o'lim holati qayd etilayotganligi, bevosita gepatotoksiklik deganda moddaning o'zi, bilvosita gepatotoksiklik deganda esa uning metabolitlari zaharliligi tushunilishi, DILI bo'yicha zamonaviy qarashlar va yondashuvlarni bergan[18].

S.F. Galimova o'zining DILI nomli maqolasida DILI mexanizmlari, tasnifi, diagnostikasi va davolash to'g'risidagi zamonaviy g'oyalar yoritilgan bo'lib, jigarning barcha ma'lum bo'lgan o'tkir va surunkali kasalliklari niqobi ostida kechishi, dori vositalari dunyoning ko'plab mamlakatlarida fulminant jigar yetishmovchiligi rivojlanishining yetakchi sabablaridan biri hisoblanishi, diagnostikasini asosida dori anamnezini sinchkovlik bilan yig'ish, boshqa mumkin bo'lgan sabablarni istisno qilish, jigar shikastlanishlari va diagnostik shkalalarni (CIOMS/RUCAM) qo'llash haqida fikrlar yuritgan[4].

Pisarev A. A. o'z maqolasida DILI jigardagi morfologik, funksional buzilishlar bilan tavsiflanishi, ular farmakologik preparatlarning keng ro'yxati tufayli yuzaga kelishi mumkinligi, DILI hozirgi vaqtda kech tashxislanadigan holat ekanligi, bu noxush kechishga olib kelishi, jigar shikastlanishining og'ir shakllarini rivojlanishiga yordam berishi va davolash samaradorligiga ta'sir qilishi, muayyan dori vositasi yoki ularning kombinatsiyalarining ta'sirlari keltirilgan bo'lib, uni diagnostikasi, davolashga yondashuvlar, antidot va gepatoprotektorlar bilan davolash va ushbu muammolarni hal qilishning dolzarb yo'nalishlarini atroflicha yoritib bergan[5].

Molostvova A.F., Xabirova G.I., Xarisova Yu.I., Salimova L.M lar o'z maqolalarida DILI bioximik ko'rsatkichlarning yengil og'ishidan tortib, o'tkir jigar yetishmovchiligigacha bo'lgan keng ko'lamli klinik holatlarni o'z ichiga olishi, jigarning aksariyat nojo'ya reaksiyalari induktor preparatlar oxirgi marta qabul qilingandan so'ng 5-90 kun oralig'ida boshlanishi, shifokorlarda DILI ni to'g'ri diagnostika qilish va davolash bilan bog'liq ko'plab hal etilmagan masalalar mavjudligi, unga birinchi navbatda, farmatsevtik preparatlarni nazoratsiz tayinlash va qabul qilish, biologik faol qo'shimchalar, oxir-oqibat polipragmaziyaning rivojlanishi va shunga mos ravishda preparatlarning gepatotoksikligini kuchaytirishi haqida ma'lumotlar berishgan[2].

Rossiya terapevtlar ilmiy tibbiyot jamiyati va Rossiya gastroenterologlar ilmiy jamiyati tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan, hamda Rossiya Federatsiyasi Sog'liqni saqlash vazirligi ilmiy kengashi tomonidan 2022-yilda tasdiqlangan katta yoshdagi kishilarda jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishi (DILI) bo'yicha klinik tavsiyanomada, DILI dagi tushunchalarga, atamalarga aniqliklar

kiritilgan bo'lib, DILI etiopatogenezi, epidemiologiyasi, tasnifi, klinik kurinishlari, diagnostikasi, diagnoz mezonlari, davolash va profilaktikasi masalalariga batafsil tuxtalishgan[19].

Ivashkin V.T., Baranovskiy A.Yu., Rayxelson K.L., Palgova L.K., Maevskaya M.V., Kondrashina E.A., Marchenko N.V., Nekrasova T.P., Nikitin I.G. lar DILI bo'yicha klinik tavsiyanomalarida epidemiologik ma'lumotlar, qo'llaniladigan atamalar, diagnostik tamoyillar, tasnifi, prognozi va DILI bilan og'riqan bemorlarni olib borish, keltirib chiqaradigan, jumladan o'limga olib kelishi mumkin bo'lgan farmakologik vositalar, dozaga bog'liq va bashorat qilinadigan, hamda dozaga bog'liq bo'lmagan va bashorat qilinmaydigan (idiosinkraziv) DILI lar, eng ishonchli diagnostik va prognostik shkalalar va indekslar, DILI patogenezi va xavf omillari, DILI ning klinik-morfologik shakllarini atroflicha bayon etishgan[6].

Drapkina O.M., Maev I.V., Axmedov V.A., Vologjanina L.G., Dolgushina A.I., Igumnova O.A., Kozlova I.V., Lazebnik L.B., Okovityy S.V., Pirogova I.Yu., Saenko A.A., Tarasova L.V., Tixonova T.A., Turkina S.V., Хлынов I.B., Хлынова O.V., сыганова Yu.V. lar tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan DILI nomli klinik tavsiyanomada, uni ta'rifi, etiopatogenezi, epidemiologiyasi, tasnifi, klinikasi, diagnostikasi, diagnostik kriteriyalari, davolash va profilaktika masalalari atroflicha bayon etilgan [1].

Xitoylik mualliflar Deng Y, Wang C, Fu Y, Li D, Ji D. 2022- yil noyabr oyidagi chop etishgan maqolalarida, jigarni dori vositalardan surunkali zararlanishida jigarda fibroz bosqichlari ortib borishi haqida ilmiy ma'lumotlar berib borishgan[7].

Dorota M. Kozielwicz, Piotr Stalke 2025yilda chor etilgan DILI nomli maqolalarida boshqa ksenobiotiklar bilan o'zaro ta'siri to'liq o'rganilmagan dori vositalari va biologik faol qo'shimchalarni iste'mol qilishning ko'payishi DILI ning ko'payishiga olib kelganligi, dori-darmonlarni o'zaro ta'siri bilan bog'liq nojo'ya ta'sirlar tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etayotganligi, bemorlarning fikriga ko'ra, o'simlik dori vositalari zararli bo'lishi mumkin emasligi va ular shifokorlarga ularni iste'mol qilish haqida xabar berishmasliklari, nojo'ya ta'sirlarning klinik manzarasi polimorfligi, ba'zi hollarda jigarning o'zgaruvchan intensivlikdagi shikastlanishi kuzatilishi, ba'zan ko'p yillardan keyin jigar sirrozi va gepatotsellyulyar karsinomasiga olib kelishi haqida ma'lumotlar berishgan.

Khoury T. et al: lar o'zlarining DILI nomli o'z maqolalarida DILI kam uchraydigan, ammo hayot uchun xavfli ekanligi, DILI o'tkir yoki surunkali jigar kasalligining har qanday morfologik xususiyatlariga ta'sir qilishi va uning gistopatologik xususiyatlari o'tkir virusli gepatit kabi jigar shikastlanishining boshqa sabablaridan farq qilmasligi, DILI ning klinik xususiyatlari, patogenezi, tashxis usullari va natijalar haqida ma'lumotlar berishgan[8].

Marwan Ghabril o'zining DILI nomli maqolsida DILI global muammo ekanligi, diagnostikasi klinik jihatdan murakkab ekanligi, jigar shikastlanishini og'ir kechishi, jigar yetishmovchiligi, o'lim yoki jigar transplantatsiyasiga olib kelishi mumkinligi, surunkali jigar kasalliklari bo'lgan bemorlarda DILI yuqori xavfli bo'lishi haqida ma'lumotlar bergan.

Paul H. Hayashi, MD, MPH and Einar S. Bjornsson, MD, PhD o'zlarining "DILI dan keyingi uzoq muddatli natijalar" nomli maqolalarida DILI ning spektri, ular yengil surunkali zararlanishdan to'kechki jigar yetishmovchiligi va o'limgacha bo'lishi mumkinligi, DILI holatlarining kichik, ammo muhim qismi tuzalmasligi, natijada surunkali shikastlanish va hatto jigar yetishmovchiligi rivojlanishi, ushbu holatlarni aniqlash va tan olish qiyinligi, jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanishi holatlarining kamdan-kam uchrashi va surunkali shikastlanishlar undan ham kam uchrashi haqida ma'lum qilishgan [9].

Paul H. Hayashi, MD, MPH Robert J. Fontana, MD o'zlarining DILI nomli maqolalarida idiosinkratik DILI bilan og'riqan bemorlar gastroenterolog uchun diagnostik, prognostik va terapevtik muammolarni keltirib chiqarishi, DILI ning namoyon bo'lishi jigar fermentlarining asimptomatik ko'tarilishidan tortib to o'tkir jigar yetishmovchiligigacha o'zgarishi mumkinligi, dori to'xtatilgandan so'ng aksariyati o'tib ketishi, bemorlarning 20% da DILI surunkali kechishi, bu esa shifokorning diagnostika va boshqaruv ko'nikmalarini yanada qiyinlashtirishi, ba'zi dori-darmonlar fibroz, ensefalopatiyaga olib kelishi mumkinligi, DILI ni aniq tashxislash uchun ob'ektiv testlar yo'qligi, sababiy bog'liqlikni baholash vositalari mavjud bo'lsada, ularning hech biri keng tarqalgan

yoki qo‘llaniladigan klinik amaliyot emasligi, klinik diagnoz to‘liq va aniq anamnez yig‘ishga, kasallikni klinik kechishini kuzatishga va jigar shikastlanishining keng tarqalgan sabablarini istisno qilishga qaratilganligi haqida ilmiy fikrlarni bildirishgan[9].

Harshad C. Devarbhavi, Cyriac Abby Philips o‘zlarining DILI nomli maqolalarida DILI dastlab jigarni bioximik taxlillari asosida jigar fermentlarining ko‘tarilishi, sirroz rivojlangan bosqichlarida bilirubin miqdorining oshishi yoki uzoq muddatli xalqaro me‘yorlashtirilgan nisbat yoki MELD (Model For End-Stage Liver Disease- jigar kasalligining yakuniy bosqichi uchun model) kabi global jigar funktsiya buzilishining birinchi belgisi bo‘lishi mumkinligi, jigarni asosiy kasalliklari (jigarni yog‘ kasalligi, steatogepatit, surunkali xolestatik kasalliklar va jigar sirrozi) bo‘lgan bemorlarda jigarni dori vositalar ta‘siridan zararlanishini aniqlash, baholash va boshqarish bo‘yicha konsensus ko‘rsaarini ishlab chiqishga harakat qilinganligi, dori vositalarni sitoxrom P450 fermentlarga ta‘sir qilishi, bu esa gepatotsitlar ichida dori ta‘sirining kuchayishiga olib kelishi, dori vositalarining nojo‘ya ta‘sirilarini oshirishi haqida ilmiy ma‘lumotlar berishgan[10].

Xitoylik boshqa bir guruh tadqiqotchilar Xitoydagi klinik sharoitlardan kelib chiqqan holda, o‘z qo‘llanmalarida, shuningdek, surunkali jigar kasalliklarida DILI uning qayta faollashuviga olib kelishiga alohida e‘tibor qaratishgan.

Yuqorida bayon etilgan tadqiqotchilar o‘z ilmiy maqolalarida DILI bo‘yicha atroflicha ilmiy ma‘lumotlar, diagnostik mezonlar, davolash buyicha tavsiyalar berishgan bo‘lsalarda, biroq surunkali virusli gepatitlarning (virus yuklamasini o‘zi jigarga ortiqcha yuk bo‘lishi, jigarda fibroz rivojlanishiga olib kelishi) fibrozsiz va fibroz bosqichlarida DILI holatlarini qiyoslab urganish masalasida aniq bir tadqiqotlar olib borilganligini topa olmadik.

Tadqiqotni maqsadi: Surunkali virusli gepatit V ning fibrozsiz va fibroz bosqichlarida DILI holatlarini qiyoslab urganish.

Tadqiqotni vazifalari:

1. Surunkali virusli gepatit V ning fibrozsiz bosqichlarida jigarni dori vositalar ta‘siridan toksik zararlanish holatlarini aniqlash.

2.Surunkali virusli gepatit V ning fibroz bosqichlarida DILI holatlarini qiyoslab aniqlash.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari. 2025- yilda Samarqand viloyatining turli tumanlarida surunkali virusli gepatit V ning fibrozsiz va fibroz bosqichlari bilan “D” nazoratida turgan bemorlarda DILI holatlari qiyoslanib o‘rganildi. Jigardagi fibroz bosqichlari FibroScan 430 (Fransiya) apparati orqali aniqlandi. Surunkali virusli gepatit S IFA va PSR usulida aniqlandi. Jigarni dori vositalar ta‘siridan zararlanishi xalqaro tibbiyot fanlari tashkilotlari kengashi CIOMS (Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences) tomonidan tavsiya etilgan R (nisbat) = ALT (MYuCh karraligi) / IF (MYuCh karraligi) bo‘yicha va sinchikovlik bilan yig‘ilgan dori anamnezi orqali aniqlandi.

O‘rganilayotgan bemorlar yoshi 20 yoshdan 75 yoshgacha bo‘lgan 388 nafar bemorlar bo‘lib, bemorlarni o‘rtacha yoshi ($Mv=(x1+x2+.....+xn)/n$) 47,5+_10 yoshni tashkil qiladi.

SVGV ga chalingan 388 nafar (shundan 40 yoshgacha bo‘lganlar 202 nafarni, 40 yoshdan kattalar 186 nafarni tashkil qiladi) bemorlarni 226 nafarida jigarda fibroz bosqichlari rivojlanmaganligi, 162 nafarida fibroz bosqichlari rivojlanganligi aniqlandi. SVGV ga chalingan 388 nafar bemorlarni 199 nafarni erkaklar, 189 nafarni ayollar tashkil qiladi.

Surunkali virusli gepatit V da jigarni dori vositalar ta‘siridan zararlanish holatlari urganilganda quyidagilar aniqlandi (2-jadval).

2-jadval

№	Fibroz bosqichlari	Kuzatilgan bemorlar soni	DILI bemorlar soni	DILI ayollar soni
SVGV ga chalingan bemorlar soni 388 nafar				
1	F -O	226	10 (4,42%)	2 (20%)
	Fibrozsiz bosqichlari	226	10 (4,42%)	2 (20%)
1	F- 0-2	128	11 (8,59%)	3
2	F-2-3	8	0 (0%)	

3	F- 3-4	13	3 (23,07%)	
4	F-4 dan yuqori	13	3 (23,07%)	
	Fibroz bosqichlari	162	17 (10,49%)	
	Jami	388	27 (6.95)	5 (18,51%)

Xulosalar.

1. Surunkali virusli gepatit V ning fibroz bosqichlari rivojlanmagan bemorlarda jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanish holatlari 4,42% ni tashkil qilganligi aniqlandi.

2. Surunkali virusli gepatit V ning fibroz bosqichlari rivojlangan bemorlarda jigarni dori vositalar ta'siridan zararlanish holatlari 10,49% ni tashkil qilganligi aniqlandi.

Tavsiyalar.

1. Surunkali virusli gepatit V ning fibroz bosqichlari rivojlangan bemorlarga hayotiy zarurat bo'lmagan holatlarda patogenetik dori vositalarni qo'llashni cheklash.

2. Surunkali virusli gepatit V da dalillarga asoslanganlik darajasi yuqori bo'lgan dori vositalarni qo'llash.

REFERENCES| ЧОККИ | IQTIBOSLAR:

1. Drapkina, O. M., Maev, I. V., Akhmedov, V. A., Vologzhanina, L. G., Dolgushina, A., Igumnova, O. A., ... & Tsyganova, Yu. V. (2024). Drug-induced liver injury (DILI) in adults. *Experimental and clinical gastroenterology*, (12 (232)), 5-48. (in Uzb)
2. Molostvova, A. F., Khabirova, G. I., Kharisova, Yu. I., & Salimova, L. M. (2022). Drug-induced liver damage: a modern view on a current problem. *Bulletin of modern clinical medicine*, 15(5), 107-115. (in Uzb)
3. Lazebnik, L. B., Golovanova, E. V., Khlynova, O. V., Alekseenko, S. A., Aryamkina, O. L., Bakulin, I. G., ... & Tsyganova, Yu. V. (2020). Drug-induced liver injury (DILI) in adults. *Experimental and Clinical Gastroenterology*, (2 (174)), 29-54. (in Uzb)
4. Галимова, С. Ф. (2011). Лекарственные поражения печени (часть 1). *Трансплантология*, (1), 13-22. (in Uzb)
5. Pisarev A. A. "Drug-induced liver damage" (DOI: 10.29039/2224-6444-2024-12-1-61-70) UDC 616.36:615.065 *Crimean Journal of Experimental and Clinical Medicine*. 2024, Vol. 14, No. 1(in Uzb)
6. Ivashkin, V. T., Baranovsky, A. Yu., Raikhelson, K. L., Palgova, L. K., Maevskaya, M. V., Kondrashina, E. A., ... & Nikitin, I. G. (2019). Drug-induced liver injury (clinical guidelines for physicians). *Russian Journal of Gastroenterology, Hepatology, Proctology*, 29(1), 85-115. (in Uzb)
7. Deng, Y., Wang, C., Fu, Y., Li, Z., & Ji, D. (2022). A high relapse risk of chronic drug-induced liver injury is correlated with a greater severity of liver fibrosis. *Nan Fang yi ke da xue xue bao= Journal of Southern Medical University*, 42(11), 1655-1661. (in Uzb)
8. Khoury, T., Rmeileh, A. A., Yosha, L., Benson, A. A., Daher, S., & Mizrahi, M. (2015). Drug induced liver injury: review with a focus on genetic factors, tissue diagnosis, and treatment options. *Journal of clinical and translational hepatology*, 3(2), 99. (in Uzb)
9. Hayashi, P. H., & Bjornsson, E. S. (2018). Long-term outcomes after drug-induced liver injury. *Current hepatology reports*, 17(3), 292-299. (in Uzb)
10. Devarbhavi, H. C., & Philips, C. A. (2024). Drug-induced liver injury in patients with underlying liver disease. *Clinical Liver Disease*, 23(1), e0189. (in Uzb)
11. Eremina Elena Yurievna Drug-induced liver damage *Practical medicine 1 (77) March 2014 UDC 615.244:616.36-031.3 Mordovia State University named after N.P. Ogarev, 430005, Saransk, Bolshevistskaya st., 68.* (in Uzb)
12. Onuchina E.V., Rozhansky A.A., Kazakova R.V., Poshkaite I.A. Drug-induced liver damage. *Siberian Medical Journal*, 2007, no. 3. Irkutsk State Medical University. (in Uzb)
13. Stine, J. G., & Chalasani, N. (2015). Chronic liver injury induced by drugs: a systematic review. *Liver International*, 35(11), 2343-2353. (in Uzb)

14. Ostapowicz, G., Fontana, R. J., Schiødt, F. V., Larson, A., Davern, T. J., Han, S. H., ... & US Acute Liver Failure Study Group*. (2002). Results of a prospective study of acute liver failure at 15 tertiary care centers in the United States. *Annals of internal medicine*, 137(12), 947-954. (in Uzb)
16. Plotnikova, E. Yu., Baranova, E. N., Vorosova, O. A., Karyagina, M. S., & Krasnov, K. A. (2020). Drug-induced liver disease. A clinical case of liver cirrhosis due to nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug use. *The attending physician*, (2), 28-34. (in Uzb)
17. DeLeve, L. D., Shulman, H. M., & McDonald, G. B. (2002). Toxic injury to hepatic sinusoids: sinusoidal obstruction syndrome (veno-occlusive disease). In *Seminars in liver disease* (Vol. 22, No. 01, pp. 027-042). Copyright© 2002 by Thieme Medical Publishers, Inc., 333 Seventh Avenue, New York, NY 10001, USA. Tel.:+ 1 (212) 584-4662. (in Uzb)
18. Brosens, I., Johannisson, E., Baulieu, E. E., Benagiano, G., Cooke, I. D., Goldzieher, J. W., ... & Westerholm, B. (1986). Oral contraceptives and hepatocellular carcinoma. *British Medical Journal* (Clinical research ed.), 292(6536), 1667. (in Uzb)
19. Chernova, V. M. (2011). Toxic liver damage: modern views and approaches to therapy. *Acute and emergency conditions in medical practice*, 2, 26-30. (in Uzb)
20. Lazebnik, L. B., Golovanova, E. V., Alekseenko, S. A., Aryamkina, O. L., Bakulin, I. G., Bakulina, N. V., ... & Tsyganova, Yu. V. (2020). Clinical guidelines: drug-induced liver injury in adults. *Therapy*, 6(4), 52-76. (in Uzb)
21. Ghabril, M., Vuppalachchi, R., & Chalasani, N. (2025). Drug-Induced Liver Injury in Patients With Chronic Liver Disease. *Liver International*, 45(3), e70019. (in Uzb)
22. Paul H. Hayashi, MD, MPH1 Robert J. Fontana, MD Clinical Features, Diagnosis, and Natural History of Drug-Induced Liver Injury *Seminars in Liver Disease* Vol. 34 No. 2/2014(in Uzb)
23. Kuznetsov, P. L., & Borzunov, V. M. (2013). Endogenous intoxication syndrome in the pathogenesis of viral hepatitis. *Experimental and Clinical Gastroenterology*, (4), 44-50. (in Uzb)
24. Balikin, V. F., & Orekhova, E. E. (2011). Clinical significance of viral load determination in chronic hepatitis B and C in children. *Childhood Infections*, 10(4), 20-25. (in Uzb)
25. Björnsson, E. S., Bergmann, O. M., Björnsson, H. K., Kvaran, R. B., & Olafsson, S. (2013). Incidence, presentation, and outcomes in patients with drug-induced liver injury in the general population of Iceland. *Gastroenterology*, 144(7), 1419-1425. (in Uzb)
26. Sgro, C., Clinard, F., Ouazir, K., Chanay, H., Allard, C., Guilleminet, C., ... & Hillon, P. (2002). Incidence of drug-induced hepatic injuries: a French population-based study. *Hepatology*, 36(2), 451-455. (in Uzb)
27. Leone, A., Nie, A., Parker, J. B., Sawant, S., Piechta, L. A., Kelley, M. F., ... & McMillian, M. K. (2014). Oxidative stress/reactive metabolite gene expression signature in rat liver detects idiosyncratic hepatotoxicants. *Toxicology and applied pharmacology*, 275(3), 189-197. (in Uzb)
28. Drug, R. R. A. (1999). Definitions of terms and criteria for their use. Geneva: World Health Organization. (in Uzb)
29. Maddrey, W. C., & Boitnott, J. K. (1977). Drug-induced chronic liver disease. *Gastroenterology*, 72(6), 1348-1353. (in Uzb)

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